

UNDERSTANDING ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACTS ASSOCIATED WITH PRODUCTION AND MARKETING OF GUAVA

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ABSTRACT

The objective of the present study was to examine the effect of production and marketing processes on environment, human health, ecosystem and resources. The life cycle assessment (LCA) of various processes and materials used during production phase of guava revealed that the production and application of agricultural inputs were the major contributors to global warming, fresh water aquatic ecotoxicity, terrestrial ecotoxicity, acidification and eutrophication as well as caused highest damage to the ecosystem. The application of zinc monosulphate as micronutrient had major impact on abiotic depletion, ozone layer depletion, human toxicity and photochemical oxidation as well as caused highest damage to human health and resources depletion. The LCA during marketing phase shows that production and consumption of polyvinyl chloride crates for packaging of guava was a major contributor to abiotic depletion, global warming, human toxicity and eutrophication, whereas consumption of electricity for storage and marketing was major contributor to marine aquatic ecotoxicity, terrestrial ecotoxicity, photochemical oxidation and acidification. The abiotic depletion, global warming, ozone layer depletion, human toxicity, fresh water aquatic ecotoxicity, marine aquatic ecotoxicity, terrestrial ecotoxicity, photochemical oxidation, acidification and eutrophication were highest in marketing supply chain involving the maximum number of supply chain partners / intermediaries.

In order to minimize the impacts of production and marketing of guava on environment, human health, ecosystem and resources, it is necessary to remodel the production and supply chain process, minimize the use of zinc monosulphate, pesticides, polyvinyl chloride crates and electricity and reduce the number of intermediaries in the marketing supply chain.

Keywords: Life Cycle Assessment, Production, Distribution, Marketing, Supply Chain, Guava, India

Cite this Article: Hena Imtiyaz, Peeyush Soni and Vimolwan Yukongdi, Understanding Environmental Impacts Associated with Production and Marketing of Guava, International Journal of Management (IJM), 15(4), 2024, pp. 113-129.

https://iaeme.com/MasterAdmin/Journal_uploads/IJM/VOLUME_15_ISSUE_4/IJM_15_04_009.pdf

1. INTRODUCTION

Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) can be used to evaluate the environmental burden associated with a product, process or activity by identifying and quantifying energy and materials used and waste released to the environment. It focusses on the entire life cycle of a product or production system, from raw material acquisition through production, use, end-of-life treatment, recycling and final disposal [1]. It can be divided into four phases namely goal and scope, inventory analysis, impact assessment and interpretation [2]. Goal and scope defines the purpose of the study as well as defines a reference unit for measuring all environmental impacts. Inventory analysis refers to the data collection for the impact assessment of the product or process on the environment. At the end interpretation of the results is performed to analyze the life cycle.

Agriculture and food production contribute largely to the consumption of resources as well as have considerable impact on the environment through production process, marketing process, processing and consumption. Agricultural sector is the major contributor towards environmental degradation leading to natural resource depletion, land degradation, air emissions and waste generation [3-6]. Life cycle assessment approach is the basis of sustainability analysis due to which in depth analysis can be done for the whole system or supply chain [7-9]. Life cycle assessment has emerged as a key tool to perform an environmental sustainability analysis of product and technologies. It provides a systematic approach for measuring the enhancement in resource productivity and facilitates the policy making process. It helps to develop a sustainable agri-food supply chain system [7,10,11].

Life cycle assessment takes into account the effect of crop production and marketing of agricultural produce on resource depletion, land use, climate change, toxicity, acidification and eutrophication [8,12,13]. Bojaca et al., [14] reported that in case of greenhouse tomato production, the infrastructure has the largest impact on environment, whereas fertilization was the major contributor for abiotic depletion, acidification and eutrophication. Further, waste management in relation to greenhouse tomato production was the main contributor to fresh water and marine aquatic ecotoxicity. The research findings [13] revealed that pesticides, machinery and fertilizer production were the source of energy consumption. The other sources of greenhouse gas emissions during production and marketing are fuel consumption, production and use of lime, plant protection chemicals, transport of agricultural inputs, machinery & agricultural produce associated with different food supply chains [8,11,13,15-17].

The emissions from agricultural and marketing activities vary largely depending on climate, soil type, farming practices and supply chain system. Fruit production is an intensive agriculture system in terms of input of pesticides and fertilizers as well as investment in capital and materials [13,18,19]. The LCA studies were conducted mostly on citrus, apricot and apples production and marketing systems [4,15,20-22]. Limited LCA studies have been conducted on tropical fruits. The challenges facing life cycle assessment of fruit production system are perennial cropping, frequent pesticide treatments and consumption of irrigation water [19,21,23-26].

India is a world leading producer of guava. In order to develop sustainable value chain management system of guava, it is essential to gain in depth knowledge regarding the effect of production process, transportation process, storage, marketing and consumption of guava on environment. Although life cycle assessment is necessary for sustainable value chain management, no studies have been conducted on guava in India. Therefore, the main objective of the present study was to evaluate the role of key factors involved in value chain towards gas emission in production, transportation, storage and marketing of guava as well as develop strategies in order to minimize impact on environment human health, ecosystems and resources.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

Life cycle assessment (LCA) is a tool for assessing the impact of production process, transportation, storage, marketing and consumption on environment. The life cycle assessment methodology is guided by the norms of the international organization for standardization [2]. It usually comprises of four phases i.e. goal and scope, life cycle inventory, life cycle impact assessment and interpretation of the results.

2.1. Goal and Scope

The main goal of the present study was to assess the environmental impacts of production and distribution / marketing of guava. The goal of the study was also to identify the opportunities to reduce the environmental impacts caused by production and distribution / marketing of guava. The cradle to distribution / marketing approach was employed in the present study. Therefore, production phase included all the processes required for land preparation (machines and energy), fertilization, irrigation, weed and pest management and harvesting as well as other auxiliary activities. The distribution/marketing phase included packaging, transportation, electricity and fuel consumption, water consumption, storage and waste disposal as well as other auxiliary activities for marketing supply chains. The functional unit is important in life cycle assessment, which helps for comparison of alternative processes, products and services supply chains [2]. The functional unit of the present study is defined as the production of 1 tonne of Guava considering the production cycle, i.e. cultivation to distribution / marketing stage.

2.2. Life Cycle Inventory

The life cycle inventory data for guava from cradle to distribution were divided into two phases, i.e. production phase and distribution phase. The inventory data for production phase were collected from producers/farmers. The inventory data for distribution phase were collected from producers, commission agents, wholesalers, retailers and consumers involved in marketing supply chains. The primary data for production phase included the use of tractor, farm machinery, sprayer, fertilizer, manure, micronutrients, pesticides, fungicides, insecticides, herbicides, water, electricity, PVC pipes, etc.

The data for production of guava were collected from forty-three guava producing farmers through direct interview at their guava orchard covering the major guava producing area of Allahabad and Kaushambi districts, India (Table 1).

Table 1. Life Cycle Inventory Data for Production Phase (Cradle to Farm Gate) of Guava

Operation / Input	Unit	Mean
1. Yield	Kg/ha	26230
2. Occupation, arable land	m ² /year	11099.74
3. Plants	Nos./ ha	369.82
4. Land preparation		
• Tractor	hp	35
• Disk plough (2 bottom)	h/ha	2.90
• Disk harrow (Double action)	h/ha	1.01
• Cultivator (9 tyne)	h/ha	2.11
• Total diesel consumption	l/h	6.93
5. Fertilization		
• Total nitrogen (N)	kg/ha	264.95
• Total phosphorus (P ₂ O ₅)	kg/ha	193.86
• Total potassium (K ₂ O)	kg/ha	55.39
• Manure	kg/ha	4019.56
• Organic fertilizer	kg/ha	45.54
• Micro nutrients		
▪ Zinc	kg/ha	45.52
6. Irrigation		
• Water use (ground water)	m ³ /ha	127.63
• Electricity consumption	kWh/ha	615.75
• Pipes (PVC)	kg/ha	186.64
7. Weed and pest management		
• Total herbicides	kg/ha	4.15
• Total fungicides	kg/ha	2.26
• Total insecticides	kg/ha	0.28
• Sprayer use (Knapsack type)	h/ha	4.56
• Petrol consumption	l/ha	0.04
8. Harvesting		
• Total labour	man-h/ha	1296.78

In distribution / marketing phase, inventory data included packaging, transportation, storage, fuel, electricity and water consumption as well as waste disposal from existing four marketing supply chains for guava such as SC₁: Producer → Consumer; SC₂: Producer → Retailer → Consumer; SC₃: Producer → Commission-agent → Retailer → Consumer and SC₄: Producer → Commission-agent → Wholesaler → Retailer → Consumer (Table 2). Further, PVC (Polyvinyl Chloride) crates were used in all the supply chain scenarios (SC₁, SC₂, SC₃ and SC₄). The PVC crates were reused until they get damaged and recycled. The fresh guava was transported in different marketing supply chains, i.e. SC₁, SC₂, SC₃ and SC₄ by road transportation system. Further, the distance of transportation in SC₃/SC₄ varied considerably when compared to SC₁/ SC₂, as illustrated in Table 2. In Indian scenario, the largest share of fresh guava is marketed through marketing supply chain SC₄, followed by SC₃, SC₂, and SC₁ respectively. In the present study it was observed that the average contribution of SC₁, SC₂, SC₃ and SC₄ supply chains in marketing of fresh guava was 13%, 24%, 28% and 35% respectively.

Table 2. Life Cycle Inventory Data for Marketing / Distribution Phase (Farm Gate to Consumers) Of Guava for Different Marketing Supply Chains (SC₁, SC₂, SC₃, SC₄)

Operation/Input	Units	Mean			
		SC ₁	SC ₂	SC ₃	SC ₄
1. Producer					
a. Packaging					
• Material used	type	PVC	PVC	PVC	PVC
• Quantity of materials	kg/tonne	75.11	74.77	78.20	75.80
b. Transportation					
• Distance	km	6.68	6.63	59.79	56.05
• Fuel consumption	l/tonne	1.81	1.82	5.83	5.29
• Fuel consumption	km/l	14.20	14.15	9.65	9.65
• Capacity of vehicle	tonne	0.26	0.26	1.11	1.11
• Time taken	h	0.56	0.56	2.50	2.56
c. Wastage	kg/tonne	20.40	20.30	43.30	43.30
2. Commission agent					
• Electricity consumption*	kWh/tonne	-	-	25.32	25.32
3. Wholesaler					
a. Transportation					
• Distance	km	-	-	-	18.95
• Fuel consumption	l/tonne	-	-	-	1.64
• Fuel consumption	km/l	-	-	-	10.55
• Capacity of vehicle	tonne	-	-	-	1.11
• Time taken	h	-	-	-	0.75
b. Electricity consumption	kWh/tonne	-	-	-	7.08
c. Wastage	kg/tonne	-	-	-	121.00
4. Retailer					
a. Transportation					
• Distance	km	-	55.45	20.90	12.90
• Fuel consumption	l/tonne	-	5.23	1.98	1.23
• Fuel consumption	km/l	-	9.65	9.65	9.65
• Capacity of vehicle	tonne	-	1.11	1.11	1.11
• Time taken	h	-	2.41	0.75	0.75
b. Electricity consumption	kWh/tonne	-	8.00	8.64	7.86
c. Tap water for cleaning**	m ³ /tonne	-	0.53	0.80	0.63
d. Wastage	kg/tonne	-	120.25	119.50	119.50
5. Consumer					
a. LDPE packaging	kg/tonne	3.43	3.43	3.56	3.48
b. Tap water for cleaning**	m ³ /tonne	0.83	0.83	0.83	0.83
c. Electricity for storage	kWh/tonne	31.84	40.37	38.91	44.31
d. Waste	kg/tonne	9.75	9.95	13.15	14.25

* Commission agent uses electricity for temporary storage of fresh guava in warehouse.

** The retailers and consumers use tap water to clean guava before selling and consumption respectively.

2.1. Life Cycle Impact Assessment

The data collected during production and distribution phases of guava were analyzed with the help of SimaPro 8.0.2 (CML – IA baseline V3.01 / EU25). The environmental impact category indicators considered in this study were abiotic depletion, global warming, ozone layer depletion, human toxicity, fresh water aquatic ecotoxicity, marine aquatic ecotoxicity, terrestrial ecotoxicity, photochemical oxidation, acidification and eutrophication.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Production phase

The life cycle assessment of guava during production phase revealed that pesticide was the highest contributor (85.91%) to abiotic resources depletion (minerals). The application of zinc monosulphate as micronutrient had substantial contribution (11.81%) to abiotic resource depletion. The other farm activities and materials such as irrigation, ploughing, harrowing, planting, application of urea, phosphate, potassium, boron, insecticide, herbicide, electricity and petrol had insignificant contribution to abiotic resources depletion (minerals). The Zinc monosulphate (21.49%), applied as micronutrient was the highest contributor to abiotic resource depletion (fossil fuel), followed by urea (19.64%), herbicide (16.42%), electricity (13.76%), phosphate (8.77%), irrigation (8.44%) and pesticides (4.47%). The life cycle assessment of guava in relation to various farm activities/ operations and materials used during production phase revealed that production process of agricultural inputs (22.52%) such as fertilizers, pesticides, insecticides, herbicides, machinery, etc. were the highest contributor to global warming, followed by application of zinc monosulphate (14.95%), urea (13.69%), electricity (13.04%), herbicides (12.35%), irrigation (7.09%), phosphate (6.50%), pesticides (3.49%) and manure (2.37%). The other farm activities and materials had insignificant contribution to abiotic depletion and global warming (Fig. 1).

The application of zinc monosulphate (43.87%) as a micronutrient was the major contributor to ozone layer depletion, followed by application of urea (18.55%), pesticides (11.82%), herbicides (6.81%), phosphate (6.12%), manure (3.78%), ploughing (2.36%), insecticides (1.18%) and irrigation (1.18%). Further, zinc monosulphate (61.52%) applied as micronutrient was the major contributor to human toxicity, followed by production process of agricultural inputs (29.51%), phosphate (2.62%), electricity (1.76%), herbicides (1.46%), urea (1.29%) and irrigation (1.09%). The production process of agricultural inputs (33.84%) was major contributor to fresh water aquatic ecotoxicity, followed by zinc monosulphate (23.49%), herbicides (14.43%), pesticides (14.16%), phosphate (6.77%) and urea (5.68%). The application of phosphate (49.44%) was the major contributor to marine aquatic ecotoxicity, followed by electricity (23.09%), herbicides (12.27%), irrigation (10.39%) and pesticides (3.02%). Other farm activities and materials used during production phase of guava had insignificant contribution to ozone layer depletion, human ecotoxicity, fresh water aquatic ecotoxicity and marine aquatic ecotoxicity (Fig. 1).

Production phase revealed that production process of agricultural inputs (65.96%) was the major contributor to terrestrial ecotoxicity, followed by application of zinc monosulphate (14.89%), phosphate (13.52%) and herbicide (4.77%). The application of zinc monosulphate (28.57%) was the major contributor to photochemical oxidation, followed by application of herbicides (19.05%), phosphate (13.26%), pesticides (12.99%), urea (9.69%), electricity (8.65%) and insecticides (1.21%). The production process of agricultural inputs (56.69%) was the highest contributor to acidification, followed by application of pesticides (9.55%), phosphate (9.40%), electricity (6.72%), urea (5.81%), herbicides (5.31%), irrigation (3.40%), manure (1.17%), ploughing (0.57%) and insecticides (0.53%).

Figure 1. Environmental impacts associated with major processes and materials for production of 1 tonne guava (Production Phase)

The results further revealed that production process of agricultural inputs (53.52%) was the major contributor to eutrophication, followed by application of pesticides (27.53%), zinc monosulphate (10.57%), herbicides (3.54%), phosphate (1.94%), insecticides (0.84%), irrigation (0.57%), electricity (0.44%) and urea (0.37%). Other farm activities and materials used for production of guava had insignificant contribution to terrestrial ecotoxicity, photochemical oxidation, acidification and eutrophication (Fig. 1).

The zinc monosulphate (43.71%) applied as a micronutrient had major impact on human health, followed by application of urea (12.90%), production process of agricultural inputs (10.53%), pesticides (9.85%), herbicides (7.75%), electricity (4.78%) and phosphate (4.62%). The production process of agricultural inputs (57.41%) such as farm machinery, fertilizers, chemicals, pesticides, insecticides and herbicides had the major impact on process of agricultural inputs (57.41%) such as farm machinery, fertilizers, chemicals, pesticides, insecticides and herbicides had the major impact on ecosystems, followed by application of zinc monosulphate (15.13%), electricity (15.85%), ploughing (4.88%), urea (4.49%) and phosphate (3.15%). Further, the application of zinc monosulphate as micronutrient (44.38%) had the highest impact on resources depletion, followed by pesticides (14.00%), urea (13.41%), herbicide (8.63%), electricity (5.62%), phosphate (4.11%), irrigation (4.02%) and manure (1.74%). Other farm activities and materials used during production phase of guava had insignificant impact on human health, ecosystems and resources (Fig. 2).

Figure 2. Damage assessment of human health, eco-systems and resources associated with major processes and materials for production of guava (Production Phase)

The aforementioned results revealed that production process had significant impacts on global warming, human health, fresh water aquatic ecotoxicity, terrestrial ecotoxicity, acidification, eutrophication and ecosystems. The previous studies carried out for life cycle assessment support the findings of the presents study [12, 19, 21, 27, 29-32]. The application of zinc monosulphate as a micronutrients had highest impacts on environment, human health and resources depletion, which has not reported in previous studies [12,27,28]. Ordikhani et al., [29] revealed that rate of nitrogen application during production phase of pistachio, nectarine, peaches and apples was major contributor in damaging natural resources, whereas the present study indicates that zinc monosulphate was the key contributor in damaging environment and natural resources. The other significant contributors for damaging of resources were use of pesticides and urea, which are in agreement with the findings of the previous studies [4,21,33]. The outcomes of other studies carried out on wide range of fruit production systems revealed that production and application of agricultural inputs, particularly fertilizers, pesticides and materials were the most important contributors towards environmental impacts, which also supports the findings of the current study [4,11,17,21,30,34].

3.2. Distribution / Marketing Phase

The life cycle assessment of guava in relation to various activities and materials used during distribution / marketing phase in supply chain SC₁ (Producer → Consumer) revealed that production and consumption of PVC crates (71.62%) for packaging of guava was highest contributor to abiotic depletion (fossil fuels), followed by consumption of electricity (11.148%), petrol (9.27%), plastic bags (5.48%) and diesel (1.44%). The PVC crates (73.62%) was the highest contributor to global warming, followed by electricity (19.97%) and LDPE plastic bags (4.78%). The PVC crates (59.32%) had highest contribution in ozone layer depletion, followed by consumption of petrol (31.80%), diesel (5.06%) and transportation (2.31%). The PVC crates (52.41%) had highest impact on human toxicity, followed by Further, consumption of electricity (43.54%) and plastic bags (4.02%). the PVC crates (56.43%) was the highest contributor to fresh aquatic ecotoxicity, followed by consumption of electricity (38.47%) and plastic bags (5.08%). Consumption of electricity (77.01%) was major contributor to marine aquatic ecotoxicity, followed by production and consumption of PVC crates (20.41%) and plastic bags (2.48%).

The consumption of electricity (60.13%) during distribution / marketing of guava had highest impact on terrestrial ecotoxicity, followed by PVC crates (33.07%), transportation (3.61%) and plastic bags(3.01%).

Figure 3. Environmental impacts associated with major processes and materials for distribution / marketing of 1 tonne of guava in supply chain SC₁ (Producer → Consumer)

The consumption of electricity (66.03%) was highest contributor to photochemical oxidation, followed by PVC crates (28.30%), petrol (2.48%) and plastic bags (2.24%). Further, the consumption of electricity (75.13%) during distribution / marketing of guava in supply chain SC₁ had major impact on acidification, followed by PVC crates (21.18%) and plastic bags (2.10%). The production and consumption of PVC crates (71.68%) had highest impact on eutrophication, followed by electricity (12.89%) and plastic bags (9.45%). The other processes / materials used during distribution / marketing of guava had insignificant impact on environment, human health, ecosystem and resources (Fig. 3).

The environmental impact associated with various processes / materials used during distribution / marketing of guava in supply chain SC₂ (Producer → Retailer → Consumer) revealed that the production and consumption of PVC crates (75.54%) for packaging of guava was the major contributor to abiotic depletion (fossil fuels), followed by electricity (8.80%), petrol (6.39%), transportation (3.39%), diesel (2.88%) and plastic bags (2.82%). The PVC crates (76.26%) had the highest impact on global warming, followed by electricity (15.10%) and plastic bags (2.42%). The consumption of petrol (51.80%) had major impact on ozone layer depletion, followed by transportation (29.00%) and PVC crates (15.17%). The PVC crates (60.87%) had major impact on human toxicity, followed by electricity (36.80%) and plastic bags (2.26%). Further, the PVC crates (64.86%) had highest impact on fresh water aquatic ecotoxicity, followed by electricity (32.20%) and plastic bags (2.93%). Consumption of electricity (72.10%) had major contribution to marine aquatic ecotoxicity, followed by PVC crates (26.25%) and plastic bags (1.55%). The electricity (45.70%) consumed for storage and marketing of guava was the highest contributor to terrestrial ecotoxicity, followed by PVC crates (35.00%) and transportation (17.00%). The electricity (57.00%) had major impact on photochemical oxidation, followed by PVC crates (33.56%), transportation (5.40%), petrol (2.01%) and plastic bags (1.28%).

Figure 4. Environmental impacts associated with major processes and materials for distribution / marketing of 1 tonne of guava in supply chain SC2 (Producer → Retailer → Consumer)

Further, the consumption of electricity (69.30%) was highest contributor to acidification, followed by PVC crates (26.84%). The production and consumption of PVC crates (77.28%) had highest contribution in eutrophication, followed by electricity (9.93%), transportation (8.50%) and plastic bags (4.25%). Other processes and materials used during distribution / marketing of guava had insignificant impact on environment, human health, ecosystem and resources (Fig.4).

The life cycle assessment of guava in marketing supply chain SC₃ (Producer → Commission agent → Retailer → Consumer) revealed that production and consumption of PVC crates (73.84%) had major impact on abiotic depletion (fossil fuel), followed by electricity (11.47%), petrol (5.59%), diesel (2.75%) and plastic bags (2.53%). The PVC crates (72.15%) had highest contribution in global warming, followed by electricity (19.08%), transport (5.84%) and plastic bags (2.11%). The analysis revealed that consumption of petrol (39.88%) had highest contribution in ozone layer depletion, followed by transport (27.02%), diesel (19.30%) and PVC crates (12.35%). The PVC crates (54.31%) had highest impact on human toxicity, followed by electricity (43.77%) and plastic bags (1.88%). Further the PVC crates (58.77%) was highest contributor to fresh water aquatic ecotoxicity, followed by electricity (38.80%) and plastic bags (2.42%). The consumption of electricity (77.60%) for distribution / marketing of guava had major impact on marine aquatic ecotoxicity, followed by PVC crates (21.20%) and plastic bag (1.15%). The electricity (52.18%) had highest contribution to terrestrial ecotoxicity, followed by PVC crates (28.99%), transportation (17.39%) and plastic bags (1.16%). The electricity (64.12%) was the highest contributor in photochemical oxidation, followed by PVC crates (28.05%) and transportation (5.31%). Further, the consumption of electricity (74.95%) had highest impact on acidification, followed by PVC crates (21.81%) and transportation (1.49%). The production and consumption of PVC crates (73.57%) had highest impact on eutrophication, followed by electricity (12.72%), transport (9.59%) and plastic bags (4.08%). The other processes / materials used during distribution / marketing of guava had insignificant impact on environment, human health, ecosystem and resources (Fig. 5).

Figure 5. Environmental impact associated with major processes and materials for distribution / marketing of 1 tonne of guava in supply chain SC₃ (Producer→Commission agent→Retailer→Consumer)

The life cycle assessment of guava in marketing supply chain SC₄ (Producer → Commission agent → Wholesaler → Retailer → Consumer) revealed that production and consumption of PVC crates (76.39%) used for packaging of guava had major impact on abiotic depletion (fossil fuels), followed by consumption of electricity (10.86%), petrol (4.63%), transportation (3.22%), plastic bags (2.45%) and diesel (2.34%). The PVC crates (74.24%) had highest contribution in global warming, followed by electricity (17.98%), transportation (5.07%) and plastic bags (2.03%). The consumption of petrol (37.33%) had major impact on ozone layer depletion, followed by transportation (26.99%), diesel (19.21%) and PVC crates (14.83%). Further, the PVC crates (56.46%) was the highest contributor to human toxicity, followed by electricity (41.96%) and petrol (3.47%). The production and consumption of PVC crates (60.83%) used for packaging of guava was the highest contributor to fresh water aquatic ecotoxicity, followed by consumption of electricity (36.81%) and plastic bags (2.35%). The consumption of electricity (76.09%) had highest contribution to marine aquatic ecotoxicity, followed by PVC crates (22.70%) and plastic bags (1.15%). The electricity (51.34%) consumed for storage and marketing of guava had major impact on terrestrial ecotoxicity, followed by PVC crates (32.27%) and transport (14.67%). The consumption of electricity (62.83%) was the highest contributor to photochemical oxidation, followed by PVC crates (30.10%). Further, the electricity (73.54%) consumed during distribution/ marketing of guava was the highest contributor to acidification, followed by the PVC crates (23.39%). The production and consumption of PVC crates (75.75%) was the major contributor to eutrophication followed by electricity (11.98%), transport (8.32%) and plastic bags (3.94%). The other processes and materials used in marketing supply chain SC₄ had insignificant impact on consumption of electricity (36.81%) and plastic bags (Fig. 6).

Figure 6. Environmental impacts associated with major processes and materials for distribution / marketing of 1 tonne of guava in supply chain SC₄ (Producer→Commission agent →Wholesaler→Retailer→Consumer)

The relative impact was estimated taking marketing supply chain SC₄ as reference (100%). The relative impacts on abiotic depletion (fossil fuel) for marketing supply chains SC₁, SC₂ and SC₃ were 36.06%, 70.36% and 81.64% respectively. The relative impacts of marketing supply chains SC₁, SC₂ and SC₃ on global warming were 34.29%, 67.92% and 81.33% respectively. The relative impacts of SC₁, SC₂ and SC₃ on human toxicity were 35.47%, 63.14% and 81.16% respectively, whereas for ozone layer depletion it was 39.54%, 83.58% and 93.55% respectively. Further, the fresh water ecotoxicity were 30.26%, 40.79% and 65.79% in marketing supply chains SC₁, SC₂ and SC₃ respectively. The relative impact on terrestrial ecotoxicity were 31.71%, 62.93% and 84.39% in marketing supply chains SC₁, SC₂ and SC₃ respectively, while it was 36.13%, 62.61% and 84.45% respectively for photochemical oxidation

Figure 7. Environmental impacts for distribution / marketing of 1 tonne of guava as influenced by different supply chains (SC₁, SC₂, SC₃, SC₄)

The relative environmental impacts of marketing supply chains SC₁, SC₂ and SC₃ on acidification were 37.36%, 60.76% and 84.61% respectively, whereas for Eutrophication relative impact values were 33.66%, 68.29% and 80.98% respectively. The above results clearly showed that environmental impacts increased considerably due to increase in number of intermediaries in marketing supply chain (Fig. 7).

The life cycle assessment for different marketing supply chains indicates that production and consumption of PVC crates for packaging had major impacts on abiotic depletion, global warming, human toxicity, fresh water aquatic ecotoxicity and eutrophication. Further the consumption of diesel / petrol and electricity during transportation and storage had major impact on marine ecotoxicity, photochemical oxidation and ozone layer depletion [35-39]. Albrecht et al., [40] revealed that wooden boxes and plastic crates used for packaging of fruits and vegetables have similar environmental impacts, whereas cardboard boxes for packaging resulted in highest environmental impacts. Further, the consumption of petrol during transportation of guava had major impacts on ozone layer depletion. Pires-Gasper [11] indicates that storage and transportation of peaches caused highest energy and fuel consumption, which consequently resulted in higher environmental impacts. The life cycle assessment of guava during distribution/marketing phase in relation to environmental impact indicators such as abiotic depletion (fossil fuel), global warming, ozone layer depletion, human toxicity, fresh water aquatic ecotoxicity, marine aquatic ecotoxicity, terrestrial ecotoxicity, photochemical oxidation, acidification and eutrophication revealed that the marketing supply chain is significantly influenced the environment due to considerable increase in number of intermediaries in marketing supply chains. This is due to the fact that operations/activities and consumption of inputs for transportation, storage and marketing increased considerably with the increase in number of intermediaries in marketing supply chains. The information to assess the effect of different marketing supply chains of fruits on environmental impacts are limited. Roy et al., [41] observed that change in cultivation, transportation and distribution/marketing process of fresh tomato contributes to reducing environmental pollution and global warming.

4. CONCLUSION

The main purpose of the present investigation was to identify the key activities in the production and marketing process of guava which have high environmental impact and to suggest strategies to minimize their impacts. The production and application of agricultural inputs such as farm machinery, irrigation, fertilizers, chemicals, pesticides and insecticides were the major contributors to global warming, fresh water aquatic ecotoxicity, terrestrial ecotoxicity, photochemical oxidation, acidification and eutrophication as well as caused highest damage to ecosystem. The application of zinc monosulphate as micro nutrient had major impact on abiotic depletion, ozone layer depletion, human toxicity and photochemical oxidation as well as had the highest impact on human health and resource depletion. Therefore, it is recommended to re-model and optimize the production and application of agricultural inputs for guava by adopting novel technologies and cultivation methods to minimize the impact on environment, human health and ecosystem.

The abiotic depletion, global warming, ozone layer depletion, human toxicity, freshwater aquatic ecotoxicity, marine aquatic ecotoxicity, terrestrial ecotoxicity, photochemical oxidation, acidification and eutrophication increased with the increase in number of intermediaries in marketing supply chains because the activities and consumption associated with packaging, transportation, storage and marketing of guava increased considerably with the increase in number of intermediaries. Therefore, it is recommended to reduce the number of intermediaries in marketing supply chain in order to minimize the operation and consumption of inputs such as PVC crates for packaging, electricity for storage and marketing and petrol/diesel for transportation in order to minimize their impacts on human health, ecosystem and environment.

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Citation: Hena Imtiyaz, Peeyush Soni and Vimolwan Yukongdi, Understanding Environmental Impacts Associated with Production and Marketing of Guava, *International Journal of Management (IJM)*, 15(4), 2024, pp. 113-129.

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